

SMA-TB

In brief

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847762.

Created by TES2A & IGTP. with the collaboration of WHC, NCTLD,
CNRS, OUS, LUMC, LIONEX and ANAXOMICS.
Designed by Raquel Villar Hernández.

SMA TB

A novel **Stratified Medicine**
Algorithm to predict treatment
responses to host-directed therapy
in **TB** patients

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Tuberculosis

Tuberculosis (TB) is a chronic, life-threatening infectious disease which poses a tremendous challenge for physicians, researchers and Health Systems, which treatment is long, based only on the drug susceptibility of the responsible infective strain and very costly in drug-resistant cases (MDR-TB). The European Region still has the highest prevalence of MDR-TB in the world. Host-Directed Therapies (HDT) have been proposed to shorten treatment length and by to improve the patients' outcomes while not increasing the risk of generating drug resistance.

As hyperinflammation is responsible of the lung damage associated to patients' worse outcomes and sequelae, one of the approaches is to add an HDT with anti-inflammatory effect to the current drug regimen to cure the patients faster while having less permanent lung damage. Because TB has a wide range of clinical forms and severity stages, any therapeutic regimen needs to be studied in clinical trials (CT) as its benefit might differ among patients. No individualized personalized medicine is possible without stratifying the patients by integrating pathogen and host factors that will predict the course of the disease and the response to the intervention.

Words from the SMA-TB coordinator

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As the coordinator of the SMA-TB project, I am both **proud and grateful for the exceptional work and dedication demonstrated by our consortium partners**. Despite numerous challenges, including the COVID-19 pandemic and a partner withdrawal due to company closure, we have successfully completed our objectives and achieved key milestones. **Our project has significantly advanced the understanding of TB, and has contributed to capacity building in South Africa and Georgia**. With a robust biobank and database, we are poised to make further strides in TB research, with potential biomarkers now identified to predict health outcomes and treatment responses.

The scientific and socio-economic impacts of SMA-TB are far-reaching. Our work has led to the clinical validation of tests and the development of an open-access capacity-building kit, benefiting not only researchers but also healthcare professionals.

The project has had a direct positive effect on employment and training opportunities, and our insights into the socio-economic status of TB patients are invaluable for future health strategies. The integration of new research methodologies and the randomised CT we have conducted have opened new avenues for research and collaboration, positioning us for continued growth in both public and private sectors.

As we reflect on our journey, it is clear **that the success of SMA-TB lies in the incredible collaboration within the consortium.** I extend my heartfelt thanks to each partner for their unwavering commitment and to our advisory boards for their invaluable guidance. Together, we have laid the foundation for future research, innovation, and continued progress in the fight against TB.

I look forward to seeing how the data and findings from this project will be further explored and applied, ensuring that our work continues to have a lasting impact on global health.

Dr. Cris Vilaplana
SMA-TB Coordinator

What did we do?

Objectives

To evaluate in a CT the potential impact of acetylsalicylic acid (ASA) and Ibuprofen (Ibu) (anti-inflammatories HDT) as adjuncts to standard therapy for drug sensitive (DS-) and MDR-TB. This, potentially, will reduce tissue damage, decrease the length of the treatment and the risk of bad outcomes.

To identify and clinically validate host and pathogen biomarkers for further selection according to their relevance in terms of their ability to predict TB course and outcomes and response to treatment thanks to data science protocol.

To generate a medical algorithm to stratify patients using network-based mathematical modelling for predicting the course of the disease and its response to the intervention, to be applied during clinical management to improve and personalise TB.

All deliverables were submitted

Work packages

WP1 Evaluation of the impact of HDT
adjunctive to standard therapy of
TB (DS and MDR-TB) in a pilot CT.

WP2 Study of the pathogen and host
factors influencing disease
outcome and predicting
response to treatment.

WP3 Data science and systems
biology approaches for
patient stratification.

WP4 Communication, dissemination
and exploitation.

WP5 Project management.

WP6 Ethics requirements

All milestones have been achieved

Who are we?

**Academisch Ziekenhuis
Leiden (LUMC)**

PI: Tom Ottenhoff

The Netherlands

**Centre National de la
Recherche Scientifique -
Institut de pharmacologie
et de biologie structurale
(CNRS-IPBS)**

PI: Jérôme Nigou

France

**Institut de Recerca Germans
Trias i Pujol (IGTP)**

PI: Cris Vilaplana

Anaxomics

PI: Judith Farrés

TES2A Europe
Consulting

**TES2A Europe consulting
and business development
SL (TES2A)**

Iwona Maciejewska

Spain

**WITS Health Consortium - Perinatal HIV
Research Unit (WHC-PHRU)**

PI: Neil Martinson

South Africa

**Oslo Universitetssykehus HF
(OUS)**

PI: Anne Ma Dyrhol-Riise

Norway

Lionex GmbH (LIO)

PI: Mahavir Singh

Germany

9 partners, 7 countries

Boards

Scientific Advisory Board

Steffen Stenger

Delia Goletti

Margarida Santos Saraiva

Pere-Joan Cardona Iglesias

Ethics Advisory Board

Petros Karakousis

Steffen Stenger

Ann Rawkins

Salome Charalambous

Data Safety Management Board

Salome Charalambous

Petros Karakousis

Sebastià Videla

Trial Steering Committee

Helen McShane

Willem Hanekom

Anne Maragarita Dyrhol-Riise

Cristina Vilaplana

Neil Martinson

Sergo Vashakidze

**National Center of
Tuberculosis and Lung
Diseases (NCTLD)**

PI: Sergo Vashakidze

Georgia

Main scientific achievements

RCT completion & enrollment

We completed the RCT with **62% of the estimated sample size, surpassing the 50% milestone** set by the EC.

Although no statistically significant differences appeared across treatment arms for the primary endpoints overall, the ibuprofen and acetylsalicylic acid arms demonstrated statistically significant benefits in certain patient subsets—both in the short and long term—when compared to placebo.

Biomarker identification

We identified **12 biomarkers** that can reflect TB severity, monitor treatment progress, highlight differences between treatment arms, or stratify patients by outcome (poor vs. good).

Diagnostic tools validated

We clinically validated a **multiplex microfluidic qPCR** test for RNA host expression, the **CD5L ICT test** (developed by IGTP and LIONEX), and an **IP-10 assay** using dried blood spots.

**Clinical validation
of tests evaluated**

Molecular characterization

14

Key molecular pathways and enclaves distinguishing responders from non-responders were identified.

An annotated molecular characterization of pulmonary TB, based on manual curation of scientific publications, is **publicly accessible at <https://zenodo.org/records/14609184>**.

Medical algorithm development

Finally, we have developed a medical algorithm to enhance patient stratification and improve TB management.

სა და ფილტვის
როვნული ცენტრი

National
and

Our communication & dissemination

43 **Communication activities**

Trade fairs, flyers, leaflets or other communication materials, communication in schools, stakeholder communication, videos, newsletters, press releases, TV and radio, social networks, website

73 **Dissemination activities**

Open-access scientific publications, oral presentations, posters, & participation in conferences.

25

**activities for
community engagement**

Reaching society

1 leaflet

Leaflet about TB

Used in TB awareness within the SMA-TB project, including TB active screening activities in vulnerable populations.

Active involvement in

2 scientific- cultural activities for general society

- IN_CERT project
- Postdata/Postscript project

CCCB Visit Exhibitions & Activities Create & Learn

Postdata / Postscript
Cartography of tuberculosis

4 Communications in mass-media: radio & TV

9 Engagement events with local communities and stakeholders.

4 Videos

4 Talks in schools

Short stories involving different stakeholders' groups, such as medical staff, researchers, and caregivers involved in SMA-TB clinical trials.

Open access repository in Zenodo with documents, templates, reports

A general-purpose research repository where any research output can be shared by its users.

Open Access Repository to **SMA-TB project** through its **European Union's Horizon 2020 agreement No 847762** (Start date: 1st Jan 2020)

More information available at:

[Cordis database](#)

[SMA-TB webpage](#)

Background and Aim of SMA-TB

Tuberculosis (TB) is a chronic, life-threatening challenge for physicians, researchers and public health. The drug susceptibility of the responsible *M. tuberculosis* complex (MDR-TB). The European Region still has the

ct outputs, which has received funding from the EC,
20 research and innovation programme under **grant**
(2020, End date: 30th June 2024).

ing infectious disease which poses a tremendous
Health Systems, which treatment is long, based only on
fective strain and very costly in drug-resistant cases
the highest prevalence of MDR-TB in the world. Host-

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content.

15 publications in scientific
peer review journals

26
communications in
conferences

Multifaceted Roles of CD5L in Infectious and Sterile Inflammation. Sanchez-Moral L, Ràfols N, Martori C, Paul T, Téllez É, Sarrias MR. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2021 Apr 15;22(8):4076. doi: 10.3390/ijms22084076. PMID: 33920819; PMCID: PMC8071174.

Host-directed therapy to combat mycobacterial infections.

Kiliç G, Saris A, Ottenhoff THM, Haks MC. *Immunol Rev.* 2021 May;301(1):62-83. doi: 10.1111/imr.12951. Epub 2021 Feb 9. PMID: 33565103; PMCID: PMC8248113.

Plasma LOX-products and monocyte signalling is reduced by adjunctive cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitor in a phase I clinical trial of tuberculosis patients. Jøntvedt Jørgensen M, Nore KG, Aass HCD, Layre E, Nigou J, et al. *Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol.* 2021 June. doi: 10.3389/fcimb.2021.669623

Identification of the most vulnerable populations in the psychosocial sphere: a cross-sectional study conducted in Catalonia during the strict lockdown imposed against the COVID-19 pandemic. Farrés J, Ruiz JL, Mas JM, Arias L, Sarrias MR, et al. *BMJ Open.* 2021 Nov 26;11(11):e052140. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2021-052140. PMID: 34836903; PMCID: PMC8628111.

The role of antibodies in tuberculosis diagnosis, prophylaxis and therapy: a review from the ESGMYC study group. Melkie ST, Arias L, Farroni C, Jankovic Makek M, Goletti D, Vilaplana C. *Eur Respir Rev.* 2022 Mar 9;31(163):210218. doi: 10.1183/16000617.0218-2021. PMID: 35264411; PMCID: PMC9489037.

Immunological hyporesponsiveness in tuberculosis: The role of mycobacterial glycolipids. Correia-Neves M, Nigou J, Mousavian Z, Sundling C, Källenius G. *Front Immunol.* 2022 Dec 2;13:1035122. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2022.1035122. PMID: 36544778; PMCID: PMC9761185.

***Mycobacterium tuberculosis* fingerprint in human breath allows tuberculosis detection.** Mosquera-Restrepo SF, Zuberogoiña S, Gouxette L, Layre E, Gilleron M, Stella A, et al. *A Nat Commun.* 2022 Dec 14;13(1):7751. doi: 10.1038/s41467-022-35453-5. PMID: 36517492; PMCID: PMC9751131.

Macrophage CD5L is a target for cancer immunotherapy. Sanchez-Moral L, Paul T, Martori C, Font-Díaz J, Sanjurjo L, Aran G, Téllez É, Blanco J, Carrillo J, et al. EBioMedicine. 2023 May;91:104555. doi: 10.1016/j.ebiom.2023.104555. Epub 2023 Apr 11. PMID: 37054630; PMCID: PMC10139961.

Disseminated tuberculosis and diagnosis delay during the COVID-19 era in a Western European country: a case series analysis. Roure S, Vallès X, Sopena N, Benítez RM, Reynaga EA, et al. Front Public Health. 2023 May 18;11:1175482. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2023.1175482. Erratum in: Front Public Health. 2023 Jun 28;11:1236874. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2023.1236874. PMID: 37275492; PMCID: PMC10233202.

***Mycobacterium manresensis* induces trained immunity in vitro.** de Homdedeu M, Sanchez-Moral L, Violán C, Ràfols N, Ouchi D, et al. iScience. 2023 Jun 16;26(6):106873. doi: 10.1016/j.isci.2023.106873. Epub 2023 May 13. PMID: 37250788; PMCID: PMC10182650.

SMA-TB: study protocol for the phase 2b randomized double-blind, placebo-controlled trial to estimate the potential efficacy and safety of two repurposed drugs, acetylsalicylic acid and ibuprofen, for use as adjunct therapy added to, and compared with, the standard WHO recommended TB regimen. Arias L, Otwombe K, Waja Z, Tukvadze N, Korinteli T, et al. Trials. 2023 Jun 28;24(1):435. doi: 10.1186/s13063-023-07448-0. PMID: 37370174; PMCID: PMC10304643.

Exhaled breath specimens subjected to point-of-care lipoarabinomannan testing. Nabeemeeah F, Sabet R, Moloantoa T, Waja Z, Pretorius Z, et al. Int J Tuberc Lung Dis. 2023 Sep 1;27(9):703-705. doi: 10.5588/ijtld.23.0128. PMID: 37608487; PMCID: PMC10443782.

A longitudinal prospective study of active tuberculosis in a Western Europe setting: insights and findings. Romero-Tamarit A, Vallès X, Munar-García M, Espinosa-Pereiro J, Saborit N, et al. Infection. 2024 Apr;52(2):611-623. doi: 10.1007/s15010-024-02184-2. Epub 2024 Feb 13. PMID: 38349459; PMCID: PMC10954962.

CD5L is upregulated upon infection with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* with no effect on disease progression. Cardoso MS, Gonçalves R, Oliveira L, Silvério D, Téllez É, Paul T, Sarrias MR, Carmo AM, Saraiva M. Immunology. 2024 Jun 23. doi: 10.1111/imm.13825. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 38922694.

Cost-effectiveness of active tuberculosis screening among high-risk populations in low tuberculosis incidence countries: a systematic review, 2008 to 2023. Gogichadze N, Sagrera A, Vicente JÁ, Millet JP, López-Seguí F, Vilaplana C. Euro Surveill. 2024 Mar;29(12):2300614. doi:10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2024.29.12.2300614. PMID: 38516785; PMCID: PMC11063676.

Teaming-up with other EU funded projects

Whenever possible, SMA-TB has teamed-up with other present and future European Commission funded projects in order to conduct joint activities. In particular:

GA N° RIA2017T-2004.
Funded by the EDCTP.

STATINTB

DRTB-HDT

GA N° 847465. Funded
in the same H2020 call
as SMA-TB.

SMA-TB

INNOVA4TB

MISTRAL

GA N° 823854. An
MSCA H2020 project.

GA N° 847943. Funded
in the same H2020 call
as SMA-TB.

ADVANCE-TB

COST Action, CA21164.
More details in next page.

We teamed up with the COST Action (CA21164) **ADVANCE-TB** and jointly organized the workshop “**Defeating tuberculosis: challenges, breakthroughs and lessons learnt from projects including clinical research**”.

This workshop was held in Barcelona on the 22nd and 23rd May 2024 and aimed to:

Gain insight into real-world international projects involving clinical research, from the perspectives of various stakeholders.

Understand the crucial factors to consider during the planning and execution phases of research projects incorporating studies or clinical trials and learn effective strategies for navigating potential obstacles.

During the workshop, several partners of the SMA-TB Consortium presented their insights and experiences from designing and implementing SMA-TB project tasks. These included Dr Jérôme Nigou (IPBS-CNRS), Dr Lilibeth Arias (IGTP), Dr Nestani Tukvadze (NCTLD), and Dr Judith Farrés (ANAXOMICS).

The poster features a teal-to-orange gradient background. At the top, it displays the 'ATB' logo and 'SMA-TB' text. The main title 'DEFEATING TUBERCULOSIS' is in bold white letters. Below it, the subtitle reads 'Challenges, breakthroughs and lessons learnt from projects including clinical research'. The dates and times are listed as 'May 22nd 2024 8:30 - 16:00 CET' and 'May 23rd 2024 9:00 - 13:30 CET'. The location is '4th Floor - Sala Sagarra'. At the bottom, there are logos for 'COEST', 'Funded by the European Union', 'IGTP', and 'ANAXOMICS'. A small disclaimer at the very bottom states: 'ADVANCE-TB COST Action: Results are representative of participants and not necessarily endorsed by the central COST Agreement Number: CA21164. SMA-TB has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101019152.'

Annual meetings & General assemblies

Kick-off meeting

IGTP-Barcelona, February 2020

2nd Annual meeting

CNRS-Toulouse, May 2022

3rd Annual meeting

NCTLD-Georgia, June 2023

WP2/WP3 seminar
OUS-Oslo, June 2024

General assemblies

- 15th Dec 2022
- 12th Sept 2024

SMA-TB Final workshop
Barcelona, December 2024
Organizers (TES2A, IGTP)

**Long lasting
benefits**

Sharing public SMA-TB results with the research community.

Strengthened collaboration with EU partners and clinical sites in South Africa and Georgia.

Enhanced experience and competitiveness in RCTs and multicountry-multipartner projects.

Training opportunities for PhD, MSc, and undergraduate students.

Collaboration and joint activities established with patient organizations.

Strategic partnerships formed in the infectious disease field.

Laboratory training and capacity building at partner sites.

Long-term contracts secured for researchers at various career stages.

Many outputs available for exploitation by the Consortium and other stakeholders.

Expertise in curating and analyzing large multiparameter databases.

Several candidates identified for further studies.

Exploitation of SMA-TB results by industrial and academic partners.

**Planning is already
underway for the next
grant application**

Conclusions & reflections

Complex RCT –
multicountry

Great
challenges

Partner
withdrawal

yet...

Further
opportunities

Large database
and biobank to
be further
exploited

SMA TB

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